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Innovations for SDG 6: Development of Novel Depth-to-Potable Groundwater Map of Anambra State, Southeast Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Electrical resistivity method was employed in this study as a valuable tool for characterizing subsurface rock types, rock property, variations with depth and potential aquifer systems with the aim of identifying viable groundwater resources across Anambra state. The study sought to achieve effective groundwater management development in order to improve the quality of livelihoods, reduces water-borne diseases and enhance food security in Anambra State. The results from the vertical electrical sounding revealed that the stratigraphy of the study area mainly composed of sandstone, gravel, sandy clay and clay with depth to the groundwater potential ranging between 60 m – 110 m, 45 m – 105 m and 120 m – 130 m in Anambra South, Central and North senatorial zones respectively. Areas like Ayamelum, Anambra East, Anambra West and partly Oyi and Ogbaru predominantly of shaly sand/clay revealed very low – low groundwater potential at the depth range of 120 - 130 meters. Mainly Anambra central predominantly Ameki Formation exhibit moderately good groundwater potential at the depth of 45 m – 105 m and depth to potable groundwater in the areas like Anambra South of predominantly Nanka Formation are prone to easy infiltration of contaminants due to lack of competent layers as protective capacity. The study inferred low resistivity value predominantly at Anambra North. Njikoka, Dunukofia, Nnewi South, Nnewi North, Idemili North, Idemili South, Onitsha, Ihiala and Ekwusigo revealed moderate resistivity range of 1000 Ω m – 1400 Ω m. Very High Resistivity Range (1600 Ω m) characterized at Orumba South and Orumba North, Aguata, Awka and Anaocha.

Keywords: Novel Depth, Electrical Resistivity, Rock Types, Viable Groundwater, Standard Development Goals (GDS 6) and Potential Aquifer

INTRODUCTION

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6) aims to ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. With badly polluted surface water bodies, Anambra State relies heavily on groundwater to meet water demands of the populace. However, lack of data on groundwater conditions leads to failures of many water borehole projects. Therefore, achieving SDG 6 in Anambra State requires innovative solutions to minimize failure rates of water boreholes and ensure reliable access to safe and affordable drinking water. Electrical resistivity, a geophysical technique that measures the subsurface electrical conductivity, offers valuable insights for addressing these challenges. This research project aims to utilize electrical resistivity data to promote sustainable groundwater development. The research targeted to develop a novel, data-driven Depth-to-Potable Groundwater Map for improved success of water boreholes and guide policymakers, communities and stakeholders in ensuring equitable access to safe and sustainable groundwater resources.

Fig. 1: Map of Anambra State highlighting the Study Locations in red.

Area of the Study

This research covered twenty – one (21) local government areas in 1the three (3) senatorial zones of Anambra State. The vertical electrical sounding geophysical data of 333 locations of the 178 communities were acquired across 21 LGAs in the study area (Fig. 1). Anambra is one of the thirty- six (36) States of Nigeria which is located geographically in the South-Eastern parts of the Country. Anambra state lies within the latitude $05^{\circ} 32'$ and $06^{\circ} 45'N$ and longitude $06^{\circ} 43'$ and $07^{\circ} 22'E$ respectively. The state is bordered by Delta state in the west, Imo state in the south, Enugu state in the east and Benue state to the north. It is made of three senatorial zones being the Anambra central senatorial zone, Anambra north senatorial zone and Anambra south senatorial zone. It has a surface area of about $6,675km^2$. It extends from the river Niger at Onitsha to the east at Oji River in Enugu State. The climate common in the study area is sub-equatorial type with rainfall varying from about 2000 mm to 2,500 mm in the east to about 1600 mm in the west. Two climatic conditions exist in Nigeria and the study area, namely the dry season and the wet season. The wet season lasts for seven months, from April to October with rainfall peaking generally in September. Dry season is about five months (November – March) marked by a Harmmattan wind that enters in late December or in the early part of January as it leads to extreme dry heat later in February and March.

Geological Setting of the Study Area

The study area is boarded by lithic fill of the southern parts of Anambra basin and Northern part of parts of Niger Delta. The late Paleocene – early Eocene Imo shale with its sandstone members (Ebenebe, Umuna and Igbaku sandstone). This was deposited during the marine transgression. Overlying the Imo shale is the Nsugbe sandstone, the Nanka sand and Ameki formation which are of Ameki Group, deposited during the middle – late Eocene regression. Imo Shale which is Paleocene to Eocene in age is the oldest formation in the Niger Delta Basin. It is predominantly clayey shale with a fine texture. May contain minor occurrences of clayey ironstone and thin sandstone bands. It is known for its marine fossils, suggesting deposition in a marine environment. The Ameki Group which is Eocene in age overlies the Imo Shale and comprises of Nsugbe Sandstone, Nanka Sandstone and Ogwashi-Asaba Formation. The lithology consists of sequence of alternating layers with varying compositions. Includes sandy shale, clayey sandstone, fossiliferous shale, and fine-grained argillaceous sandstone with thin limestone bands. Its Fossiliferous nature indicates a marine environment during deposition. Fig. 2 shows geological setting of the study area highlighting some locations.

Fig. 2: Map showing the Geology of the Selected Area in Anambra state

Drainage and Hydrology

Anambra state possesses abundant surface water and the state is well drained. The major river systems are the Anambra drainage system to the west and the Mamu sub-basin all of which flow into the river Niger. West of the escarpment the Anambra and Idemili rivers carry most of the runoff. The runoff coefficients of the two drainage basins are 0.20 and 0.30 respectively. Most of the rainfall goes to recharge the groundwater in the sedimentary rocks underlying the state. The main tributaries of the Anambra river are Adada, Nwuyi and Mamu rivers, all flowing west into the Niger river. Most of the rivers in the eastern part of the Nigeria have recently been gauged. Mostly rivers are perennial due to the recharging of river flow by the underlying groundwater storage in the sedimentary aquifer of the state. The discharge measurements of Mamu river at Amansea is shown in table 1 below;

Table 1: Discharge Measurement of Mamu River at Amansea (m²/sec) (modified by Anambra Imo River Basin Development Authority)

DATE	MEAN VELOCITY	DISCHARGE
19.5.80	0.37	26.94
23.5.80	0.39	20.04
23.6.80	0.36	19.94
26.7.80	0.90	116.79
30.7.80	0.63	66.12
28.8.80	0.60	63.29
2.11.80	-	25.78
2.12.80	0.35	19.67
27.1.81	0.36	15.46
16.10.81	0.75	92.65

Data & Methodology

This study employed a novel integrated data approach to create a Depth-to-Potable Groundwater Map of Anambra State. Inferring potential depth to potable groundwater involved careful collation and analysis of existing borehole data on groundwater levels and quality across the 179 communities in the state. Geophysical field investigation was carried out to fill data gaps. The common geophysical method employed in this research is the electrical resistivity method. This method makes use of variations in the electrical properties of the subsurface, studying the geological formation of interest in relation to their depth. The resistivity of a formation is known to largely depend on the moisture content, the physical and chemical properties of the saturated water. The resistivity of a rock stratum is defined as the resistance in Ohms of a 3-dimensional volume of the earth's substance (Nwozor, K. K. and Egboka B. C. E, 2007). The equipment used for the field work was ABEM signals average system (SAS) 300 Terrameter. The apparent resistivity, which is the normal quantity determined from the field measurement reflects the distribution of the true resistivities in the subsurface, also depends on the spatial configuration of the measuring systems. Most commonly used methods for measuring earth resistivity are those in which current is driven through the ground using galvanic contact. Where four – terminal electrode arrays are used since the effect of material near the current contacts can be minimized. As Current is driven through one pair of electrodes (A & B), the potential established in the earth by this current is measured with the second pair of electrodes (M & N) connected to a sensitive voltmeter (Fig. 3). Apparent resistivity of the subsurface is determined effectively, the equation below is commonly use.

$$\rho_a = \pi(L^2 - b^2)R/2 \quad \text{where; } \rho_a = \text{Apparent Resistivity in ohm-meter}$$

L = Distance between current Electrodes

B = Distance between potential Electrodes

R = Resistance of the ground.

Fig. 3: Current Flow through Earth

RESULTS & INTERPRETATION

Layers of 333 VES locations were modeled in profile using win-resistivity software. The layers were tabulated with their respective lithologies, depths, thicknesses and curve characteristics according to their structured resistivities. Three hundred and thirty-three (333) VES locations of 21 local governments was interpreted and summarized. Interpretation of formation for each local government detailed significant effects to groundwater resources and infrastructural development in the study area. From the win-resistivity modelled profiles each layers showed some distinct curve characteristics, the layers are defined by the degree of their respective resistivities. Number of layers for VES location is determined by the modelled resistivity number, thus, the undetermined thickness is the thickness of the last layer resistivity whose depth is determined as the product of the immediate layer thickness and layer depth above. The thicknesses and depths of the overburden layers to the last layers are modelled from the win-resistivity software in accordance with their respective layers' resistivity. The root mean square to every modelled locations is rated at negligible standard of not more than 5% RMS error, showing lesser interference or abnormality in detecting the formation of the subsurface at respective locations. In each locations of the study area presents a resistograph that is plotted using win-resistivity software, each resistograph represents the plots of apparent resistivity (ohm meter) against current electrodes (AB/2), sample shown in fig.4 (selected locations). Table 2 represents interpreted electrical data of the subsurface layers of selected locations of the study area.

Fig. 4: Winresistivity plots of apparent resistivity against AB/2 of selected Locations in study area.

Geophysical and Geological Interpretation of the subsurface at Iwuamaka Primary School, Agulu Zigbo

The geological characteristics of each layer have varying implications for infrastructure development:
 Layer 1 Top layer/Laterite (2517.0 Ωm, 1.2 m thick): The presence of laterite at shallow depths can provide a stable foundation for light structures but may pose challenges for deep-foundation construction. This material can be excavated and used as a construction material for road base and embankment fill.

Layer 2 Siltsand (9205.0 Ωm, 1.3 m thick): The suitability of siltsand for infrastructure development depends on its specific properties. Siltsand can exhibit a mix of properties inherited from silt and sand,

which could impact its bearing capacity and settlement characteristics. Further investigations are recommended to assess the material properties and design requirements.

Layer 3 Shalysand (348.9 Ωm , 2.7 m thick): The properties of shalysand, such as its strength and compressibility, need to be evaluated to determine its suitability for infrastructure development. Shalysand can exhibit a mix of properties inherited from both shale and sandstone, which could influence its performance under various loading conditions.

Layer 4 Sandstone (14954.0 Ωm , 34.7 m thick): Sandstone is a sedimentary rock with varying strength, durability, and weathering properties. The suitability of this layer for infrastructure development depends on its mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, tensile strength, and fracture density.

Layer 5 Water-Saturated Sand (3284.0 Ωm , undetermined thickness): This layer extends from a depth of 39.9 meters to an undetermined depth and can be targeted for groundwater exploration and development. The presence of water-saturated sand should be carefully considered in infrastructure development, especially in terms of foundation design and groundwater control measures. This layer can provide challenges for infrastructure development due to potential issues such as settlement, liquefaction, and water seepage.

Geophysical and Geological Interpretation of the subsurface at Nduani, Agulu Zigbo

The geological characteristics of each layer have varying implications for infrastructure development:

Layer 1 Top layer/Laterite (494.0 Ωm , 1.2 m thick): The presence of laterite at shallow depths can provide a stable foundation for light structures but may pose challenges for deep-foundation construction. This material can be excavated and used as a construction material for road base and embankment fill.

Layer 2 Shalysand (1135.0 Ωm , 4.0 m thick) and Layer 4 Shalysand (1922.0 Ωm , 11.6 m thick): The properties of shalysand, such as its strength and compressibility, need to be evaluated to determine its suitability for infrastructure development. Shalysand can exhibit a mix of properties inherited from both shale and sandstone, which could influence its performance under various loading conditions.

Layer 3 Siltsand (6116.0 Ωm , 5.6 m thick): The suitability of siltsand for infrastructure development depends on its specific properties. Siltsand can exhibit a mix of properties inherited from silt and sand, which could impact its bearing capacity and settlement characteristics. Further investigations are recommended to assess the material properties and design requirements.

Layer 5 Sandstone (7389.0 Ωm , 74.0 m thick): Sandstone is a sedimentary rock with varying strength, durability, and weathering properties. The suitability of this layer for infrastructure development depends on its mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, tensile strength, and fracture density.

However, layers with lower resistivity values, such as Layer 2 and Layer 4 (Shalysand), could have some potential for groundwater exploration. Further investigations, such as drilling and geophysical studies, are recommended to determine the groundwater potential in this area.

Table 2: Interpreted Layers of VES 1-20 Locations at Anaocha LGA

Station ID/ Layers	App Res (Ω m)	Thickness (m)	Depth (m)	Description
VES 1(IGWUAMAKA PRIMARY SCHOOL AGULUZIGBO) (RMS: 2.2%)				
CURVE TYPE KHK($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 > \rho_5$)				
1	2517.0	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	9205.0	1.3	2.5	Siltsand
3	348.9	2.7	5.2	Shalysand
4	14954.0	34.7	39.9	Sandstone
5	<u>3284.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	74.6	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 2(NDUANI AGULUZIGBO) (RMS: 1.0%)				
CURVE TYPE AAK($(\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4 > \rho_5)$)				
1	494.0	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	1135.0	4.0	5.2	Shalysand
3	6116.0	5.6	10.8	Siltsand
4	1922.0	11.6	22.4	Shalysand
5	7389.0	74.0	96.3	Sandstone
6	<u>4243.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	170.3	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 3(UMUOWELLE AGULU) (RMS: 0.4%)				
CURVE TYPE QHA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)				
1	292.4	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	255.7	4.0	5.2	Shalysand
3	407.7	5.6	10.8	Siltsand
4	91.5	35.6	46.4	Shale
5	143.1	49.9	96.3	Water-Saturated Sand
6	<u>722.6</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	146.2	Sandstone
VES 4(RONI FARMS LTD AGULU) (RMS:0.8%)				
CURVE TYPE KA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$)				
1	457.0	6.3	6.3	Top layer/Laterite
2	1089.0	5.7	12.0	Sandstone
3	8.9	36.5	48.5	Shale
4	<u>50.8</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	85.0	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 5(ST.MARY CATHOLIC CHURCH UMUNRI NENI) (RMS: 1.5%)				
CURVE TYPE AQ($(\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4)$)				
1	1133.0	3.3	3.3	Top layer/Laterite
2	1964.0	16.8	20.1	Siltsand
3	13607.0	26.7	46.8	Water-Saturated Sand
4	<u>12.7</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	73.5	Shale
VES 6(UMUDIOKA VILLAGE NENI)				
CURVE TYPE QHA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)				

(RMS: 0.9%)

1	202.6	0.8	0.8	Top layer/Laterite
2	26.0	3.2	4.0	Shalysand
3	8.5	4.3	8.2	Shale
4	46.8	46.1	54.4	Shalysand
5	<u>181.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	<u>100.5</u>	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 7 (UMURU AMAZI-ANI) (RMS: 1.8%)				CURVE TYPE AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)

1	367.0	0.9	0.9	Top layer/Laterite
2	1271.0	6.3	7.2	Shalysand
3	3214.0	36.2	43.4	Siltsand
4	11094.0	43.8	87.2	Sandstone
5	937.0	84.6	171.8	Water-Saturated Sand
6	<u>19000.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	<u>256.4</u>	Sandstone
VES 8(UMURU VILLAGE ADAZI-ANI) (RMS:2.5%)				CURVE TYPE HA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$)

1	276.3	3.5	3.5	Top layer/Laterite
2	5894.7	6.2	9.7	Sandstone
3	4340.0	27.5	37.3	Siltsand
4	<u>10607.2</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	<u>64.8</u>	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 9(OBEAGU) (RMS:1.3%)				CURVE TYPE KHA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)

1	405.0	1.2	1.2	Top layer/Laterite
2	13328.0	3.4	4.6	Sandstone
3	1429.0	16.9	21.5	Siltsand
4	213.0	146.0	167.5	Water-Saturated Sand
5	<u>14225.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	<u>313.5</u>	Sandstone
VES 10(URUOFOLO VILLAGE NRI) (RMS: 1.3%)				CURVE TYPE KHA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)

1	112.0	2.0	2.0	Top layer/Laterite
2	1153.0	2.8	4.8	Sandstone
3	97.4	24.9	29.7	Shalysand
4	12.1	81.4	111.1	Shale
5	<u>2554.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	<u>192.5</u>	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 11(ADAZI-NNUKWU) (RMS: 1.1%)				CURVE TYPE HK($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4$)

1	62.4	0.8	0.8	Top layer/Laterite
2	18.7	9.5	10.3	Shale
3	348.0	11.4	21.7	Sandstone
4	<u>10.2</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	<u>33.1</u>	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 12(ADAZI NNUKWU) (RMS: 1.0%)				CURVE TYPE HA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$)

1	221.0	1.6	1.6	Top layer/Laterite
2	56.4	13.2	14.8	Shale

3	586.0	243.0	257.8	Water-Saturated Sand
4	<u>13856.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	500.8	Sandstone
VES 13(AKWAEZE)				CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 1.7%)				AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	1326.9	1.0	1.0	Top layer/Laterite
2	1677.4	2.7	3.6	Siltsand
3	1458.6	5.0	8.6	Shalysand
4	4189.2	17.8	26.4	Sandstone
5	17528.6	29.7	56.1	Water-Saturated Sand
6	<u>2956.6</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	85.8	Sandstone
VES 14 (AKWAEZE)				CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 1.9%)				KA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$)
1	120.4	2.5	2.5	Top layer/Laterite
2	333.4	7.6	10.2	Siltsand
3	50949.4	31.0	41.1	Sandstone
4	<u>868.3</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	72.1	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 15(OBELEDUANI VILLAGE OBELEDU)				CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 3.1%)				AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	164.1	1.0	1.0	Top layer/Laterite
2	926.0	1.5	2.6	Shalysand
3	54786.1	4.7	7.2	Sandstone
4	20312.1	9.7	17.0	Siltsand
5	304.8	31.3	48.3	Shale
6	<u>41478.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	78.6	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 16(EZELE VILLAGE OBELEDU)				CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 1.4%)				KA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$)
1	283.0	2.4	2.4	Top layer/Laterite
2	20293.0	4.4	6.7	Sandstone
3	843.9	18.4	25.1	Siltsand
4	<u>7130.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	43.5	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 17(IHUANA VILLAGE) (RMS: 1.0%)				CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 1.0%)				QHA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	2767.0	0.8	0.8	Top layer/Laterite
2	427.0	0.8	1.6	Shalysand
3	2091.0	1.7	3.3	Sandstone
4	630.0	4.9	8.2	Siltsand
5	<u>6005.0</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	13.1	Water-Saturated Sand
VES 18 (ADAZI-ENU)				CURVE TYPE
(RMS: 3.0%)				AKH($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)
1	507.2	0.9	0.9	Top layer/Laterite
2	2152.3	10.2	11.1	Siltsand
3	19950.0	24.9	36.1	Sandstone
4	2537.7	60.9	96.9	Water-Saturated Sand
5	<u>64993.2</u>	<u>Undetermined</u>	157.8	Sandstone

VES 19(UBURU ICHIDA)
(RMS: 3.8%)

CURVE TYPE
AHA($\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4 < \rho_5$)

1	32.7	0.9	0.9	Top layer/Laterite
2	3066.5	3.5	4.5	Shalysand
3	16573.6	21.6	26.1	Siltsand
4	33814.5	25.8	51.8	Sandstone
5	865.0	12.0	63.9	Water-Saturated Sand

6 79729.2

VES 20(ICHIDI)
(RMS: 3.0%)

CURVE TYPE
HKA($\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$)

1	1071.9	1.5	1.5	Top layer/Laterite
2	269.0	1.4	2.9	Shale
3	38032.0	7.0	9.8	Sandstone
4	3505.0	27.8	37.6	Siltsand
5	52963.4	Undetermined	65.4	Water-Saturated Sand

Undetermined 75.9 Sandstone

Occurrence Rating and Correlation of Recognized Lithology in the Study Area.

Table 3: Summarized Lithological Composition of the Study Area

Local Government Area	Predominant Sediment	Drilled Depth (m)	Water Table (m)	Sandstone Level (m)	Shale (m)
Njikoka	Shale/Sandstone	160	70	160	5-65
Dunukofia	Shale/Sandstone	140	45	140	2-40
Anaocha	Shale/Sandstone	100	80	130	5-80,120-145
Idemili South	Sandstone	140	140	120-180	5-40,75-110
Idemili North	Shale	180	180	120-180	5-70
Awka South	Shale/Sandstone	190	190	90-180	10-90
Awka North	Sandstone	190	190	85-190	5-75
Anambra Central Senatorial Zone					
Ogbaru	Sandstone/Shale	135	100	50-100,130	2-8,35-55
Onitsha North	Shale	150	95	50	2-70
Onitsha South	Shale	110	110	150	2-80,110-140
Anambra East	Shale	130	90	55-85,130	5-40
Anambra West	Sandstone	60	40	20-40,120	75-120
Oyi	Shale	160	120	120-160	20-110
Ayamelum	Shale	80	40	30-40,130	85-120

Anambra North Senatorial Zone					
Orumba South	Sandstone	65	60	60	2-20
Orumba North	Sandstone	45	30	45	2-25
Aguata	Sandstone	55	45	55	2-15,25-40
Nnewi South	Sandstone	50	25	50	4-25
Nnewi North	Sandstone	60	65	12-55	4-9
Ekwusigo	Sandstone/Shale	65	65	10-50	20-50
Ihiala	Shale	66	45	15-65	25-40
Anambra South Senatorial Zone					

Table 3 above summarized the occurrence rate of recognized lithology of the study area from the modelled win-res plots of apparent resistivity and current electrode of each local government locations of the study area. Number of top soil and saturated sand occurred with respect to number of locations acquired in each L.G.A of Anambra State. Some areas are observed to have much number of shale occurrence much equivalent to the number of locations of the local government while some areas are of less shale occurrence. Some LGA showed high to equal proportion of dry sand while some LGA showed less proportion of dry sand to number of locations surveyed.

Fig. 5: Correlation of Geoelectric Sections of Anambra Central

Fig. 6: Correlation of Geoelectric Sections of Anambra North and Anambra South

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 represent the geoelectric sections of the three senatorial zones correlated with their respective borehole logs. Anambra State's groundwater depth varies significantly across Local Government Areas. Shallow water tables (50 m) occur in Orumba North, Aguata, Nnewi South, Nnewi North, Ihiala, Anambra East, Anambra West, Ayamelum, Dunukofia and Anaocha, indicating moderate to high groundwater potential. Moderate water tables (50 -100 meters) are found in Orumba South, Ekwusigo, Ogbaru, Onitsha North, Onitsha South and Njikoka. Deep water tables (100 m) characterize Oyi, Idemili South, Idemili North, Awka South and Awka North (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6). Geological factors influencing groundwater depth include sediment type, drilling depth and geological structure. Sandstone

areas tend to have shallower water tables, Sandstone-dominated areas (Orumba South, Orumba North and Aguata) while shale-dominated areas have deeper water tables. whereas shale-dominated areas (Ihiala and Oyi). Spatially, Anambra South Senatorial Zone generally has shallower water tables, while Anambra North and Central Zones have deeper water tables. The season fluctuation in water table explained the rate of recharge and discharge during precipitation in water cycle with respect to certain factor that controls the distribution of groundwater in the study area. The observed factors that controls the distribution of groundwater in Anambra state; the geology of the area, climate, human and economic activities. The stated factors geologically affect the types of aquifer encountered in the study area. The ability of an aquifer to produce water depends on the properties of the aquifer rock formation which is the porosity and permeability. The zone of saturation in the study area posed confined and unconfined aquifers in the region of Anambra central and Anambra south respectively due to predominant formation. The confined aquifers are the closed aquifer with impermeable layer above the water table. The water in a confining aquifer is said to be under pressure due to overlying impermeable layer. Unconfined aquifer has a permeable layer as the zone of aeration or unsaturated zone which can easily replenished.

Evaluation of Resistivity from VES Analysis of each LGA to Infer Potential Potable Depth to Groundwater of Anambra State.

From the interpreted layers of the study area, parameters are evaluated for better understanding of groundwater management and infrastructural development in the study area. Those parameters are resistivity of the saturated depth which is gotten as the summed apparent resistivity of the saturated layer, measured in ohms meter. Depth to groundwater is the depth (m) that is fully saturated with water, that is water saturated sand. Depth to competent rocks is the depth (m) corresponding to the top of the layer considered competent from the given table. Thickness of weathered zones is the thickness of layers considered as weathered zones while weathered zones are the weak zones in the modelled profile of apparent resistivity and current electrodes.

Fig. 7: Distributions of Aquifer Apparent Resistivity Map of Anambra State

The interpretation of apparent resistivity data in Anambra State provides shows into subsurface geological and hydrogeological conditions, which influence groundwater resources and infrastructure development (Fig. 7).

These zones (Ayamelum, Anambra East and Anambra West) are typically associated with clay-rich formations which generally exhibit very low resistivity. Groundwater potential is limited in this area, and infrastructure development may require alternative water sources or advanced extraction techniques. Special engineering considerations are necessary for construction due to low-bearing capacity and potential settlement issues. Ranging 100 Ωm – 400 Ωm .

Low Resistivity range (400 Ωm – 900 Ωm): Domains with low resistivity values (oyi) often indicate the presence of silty or clayey materials, as well as moderately weathered zones. Groundwater potential in these areas is moderate and depends on specific geological and hydrological conditions.

Thorough assessments of aquifer properties, recharge rates, and water quality are necessary for informed decision-making and sustainable resource management. Engineering interventions may be required to address ground stability and settlement issues during infrastructure projects.

Moderate Resistivity Range (1000 Ωm – 1400 Ωm): Regions (Njikoka, Dunukofia, Nnewi South, Nnewi North, Idemili North, Idemili South, Ogbaru, Onitsha, Ihiala and Ekwusigo) with average resistivity values typically consist of sandy or mixed sedimentary formations, indicating moderate to good groundwater potential, depending on permeability and aquifer thickness. Sustainable water resource management practices are essential to ensure long-term resource availability and quality. Infrastructure development in these areas may necessitate advanced resource management strategies to balance utilization and conservation efforts.

Very High Resistivity Range (1600 Ωm): Very high resistivity values (Orumba South and Orumba North, Aguata, Awka and Anaocha) typically indicate the presence of competent bedrock or crystalline formations, which can lead to challenges in exploration and extraction. Infrastructure development in these regions presents significant challenges due to the depth of competent bedrock and the geotechnical properties of weathered materials.

Fig. 8: Distributions of Potable Depth to Groundwater Map of Anambra State

Ayamelum and Anambra West shows low groundwater potential at about depth range of 120 - 130 meters (Fig. 8). The geology typically comprises highly impermeable materials, such as clay. Commonly used in this area is surface water. Geology may consist of a mix of permeable and semipermeable materials. Sustainable water resource management practices are essential to ensure longterm resource availability and quality. Infrastructure development in these areas may require engineering interventions to address ground stability and settlement issues. Orumba North, Orumba South and Aguata revealed high depth to groundwater potential due to the geological constituent of those area basically dry sand and very coarse sandstone. The depth of saturation range is easily contaminated because of little or no presence of impermeable layers at the overburden. The results conclude rest local government of Anambra state within Nanka and Ameki formation show moderately groundwater potential. The geology usually consists of thick sedimentary formations or fractured bedrock. Infrastructure development presents significant challenges of weathering and erosion due to lack of competency. Infrastructure projects may necessitate advanced resource management strategies to balance utilization and conservation efforts while engineering solutions are needed to address ground stability and settlement concerns.

CONCLUSIONS

This study utilized integrated datasets and innovative methodologies to develop Depth-to-Potable Groundwater Map of Anambra State as a support tool for SDG 6. The embedded solutions can help reduce water borehole failures and guide policy decisions on groundwater exploration and development to improve access to clean water for Ndi Anambra.

The novel depth-to-potable groundwater map reveals:

- Depth-to-groundwater and optimal drilling depths across the state

- Communities that require shallow-depth (≤ 50 m) boreholes
- Communities that require medium-depth (≥ 50 m ≤ 100 m) boreholes
- Communities that require very deep (> 100 m) boreholes
- Relationships between geology, hydrology and groundwater quality

REFERENCES

- Abam, T. K. S. (2001). Regional hydrological research perspectives in the Niger Delta. *Journal of Hydrological Sciences*, 46:13-25.
- Abiola, O., Oladapo, M.I. and Akintorinwa, O.J. (2009). Protective capacity of an aquifer and longitudinal unit conductance of layers above the aquifer. *International Journal of Physical Sciences*, 4 (3):120 – 132.
- Egboka, B. C. E., & Nwankwo, E. A. (2015). Hydrogeological Characteristics and Groundwater Quality Assessment of the Ogbaru Wetlands, Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, 3(4): 213-223.
- Ehirim, C.N. and Ebeniro, J.O. (2010). Evaluation of aquifer characteristics and groundwater potentials in Awka, South East Nigeria, using vertical electrical sounding. *Asian Journal of Earth Sciences* Vol. 3 (2), pp. 7381.
- Ekwe, A.C., Onuoha, K.M. and Onu, N.N. (2006). Estimation of aquifer hydraulic characteristics from electrical sounding data: the case of middle Imo River basin aquifers, south- eastern Nigeria. *Journal of spatial hydrology*, 6 (2): 121 – 126.
- Eze, C.C. (2012). Hydro-geophysical studies for the delineation of potential groundwater zones in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Int Res J Geol Min*, 2 (5): 103-112.
- Gebrehiwot, A.B., Tadesse, N. and Jigar, E. (2011). Application of water quality index to assess Suitability of groundwater quality for drinking purposes in Hantebet watershed, Tigray, Northern Ethiopia. *ISABB J Food Agric Sci.*, 1 (1): 22–30.
- Ibekwe, A.M. and Anyaduba, J.C. (2015). Hydrological Processes in changing Climate and land. *Journal of Water and Land Development*, 24 (1): 1 – 10.
- Keys, W. S. (1990). Borehole geophysics applied to groundwater investigation, United States Geological Survey techniques of water resource investigation, *Techniques of Water Resources Investigations*, 150.
- Kelly, W.E. (1977). Geoelectrical sounding for estimating aquifer hydraulic conductivity. *Groundwater*, 15 (4): 420-424.
- Niwa, S. and Singhal, D.C. (1981). Estimation of aquifer transmissivity from Darrouk parameters in porous media. *Journal of Hydrology*, 6 (50): 393-399.
- Niwa, S. and Singhal, D.C. (1985). Aquifer transmissivity of porous media from resistivity data. *J. Hydro.*, 82 (9): 143-153.
- Nwajide, C.S. and Reijers, T.J.A (1996). Geology of the southern Anambra Basin in: Reijers, T.J.A.(ed). *Selected chapters on geology of Warri: Shell Petroleum Development Company*, 133 – 148.
- Nwajide, C.S. and Reijers, T.J.A (1996). Geology of the Southern Anambra Basin. In:Reijers, T.J.A. (Ed.), *Selected Chapters on Geology*. SPDC, Warri, 133–148.
- Nwozor, K.K. and Egboka, B. C. E (2007). Geophysical Exploration for Groundwater Recourses in some satellite communities in awka capital territory, Anambra State, Nigeria. *Natural and Applied Sciences Journal*, www.nasjpr.com 8 (1): 8591
- Nwozor, K. K., Chiaghanam, O. I. and Onuorah, L.O (2015); Borehole Annulus- Filling Materials and Enrichment of Heavy Metals in Eocene Palaeocene Aquifer Systems in Awka, Southeast Nigeria. *British Journal of Applied Science (BJAST)*, 8 (3): 206 - 285.
- Offodile, M. E. (2002). Geology and Groundwater Resources of Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Mining and Geology*, 38(1): 61-67.

- Okoli, O. C. and Ibenwa, C. A. (2016). Characterization of Physico-Chemical and Heavy Metal Pollution of Surface Water in Anambra State, South East Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 6 (3): 39-52.
- Okoro, E.I., Egboka, B. C. E. and Onwuemesi, A. G (2010). Evaluation of the aquifer characteristic of Nanka Sands using hydrogeological method in combination with Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES). *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.* June,14 (2): 5 – 9.
- Okwueze, E. E. (1996). Preliminary findings of the groundwater resources potentials from a regional geoelectric survey of the Obudu basement area, Niger. *Global J. Appl. Pure Sci.* 2:210-211.
- Oladapo, M.I. and Akintorinwa, O.J. (2007). Hydrogeophysical study of Ogbese Southwestern, Nigeria. *Global J. Pure and Applied Sci.*, 131 (24): 55-61.
- Onwuemesi, A. U. (1990). Hydrogeophysical and geotechnical properties of soils in Nsukka and environs, southeastern Nigeria. *Environmental Geology and Water Sciences*, 16(2): 81-88.
- Onwuemesi, A.G. and Egboka, B.C.E. (2006). 2-D polynomial curve fitting techniques on water table and hydraulic gradients estimations in parts of Anambra Basin, Southern Nigeria. *Natural and Applied Sciences Journal*, 8:6-13.
- Onyenweife, G. I., Nwozor, K. K., Onuba, L. N., Nwike, I.S. and Egbunike, M. I. (2020). Estimation of Aquifer Parameters in Awka and environs, Anambra State, Nigeria, using Electrical Resistivity Method. *International Journal of Innovative Scientific and Engineering Technologies Research*, 8 (4): 1–29.
- Oseji, J. O. (2010). Geo-electric investigation of groundwater resources and aquifer characteristics in Utagba-Ogbe Kingdom Nvokwa Land Delta State Nigeria; *J. Env. Chemistry and Ecotoxicology* 2: 38–46.
- WHO, (2011). World health organisation guidelines for drinking water quality. Geneva. 4th Edition, 1-518.